

MATEMATIKA FANI RIVOJI MASALASIDA SHARQ OLIMLARINIG HISSASI

Abdullayeva Xurshida Shoqosim qizi,
Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani 2 son kasb hunar maktabi
matematika fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada matematika fani rivojiga Xindiston, arabiston, O'rta Osiyo mamlakatlarida yetishib chiqqan olimlarning xissasi qay darajada bo'lganligi haqida fikrlar bildiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Matematika, manfiy, son, ko'paytirish, amaliyot.

Аннотация: В статье высказаны мнения о вкладе ученых Индии, Аравии и Центральной Азии в развитие математики.

Ключевые слова: Математика, отрицание, число, умножение, практика.

Abstract: The article expresses opinions on the contribution of scientists who grew up in India, Arabia, and Central Asia to the development of mathematics.

Keywords: Mathematics, negative, number, multiplication, practice.

Matematika fanini rivojlantirishda xind olimlarining xissalari ayniqsa katta bo'lgan. Ular fanda musbat, manfiy son kabi yangi matematik tushunchalarni kiritganlar, ichki chizilgan kupburchak yuzini, jismlar xajmini hisoblash usullarini, amallar va ularni bajarish tartibini aniklaganlar. Masalan, nol, manfiy son tushunchalarini kiritishda Ariabxatta (V asr), manfiy sonlarda kushish va ayirish amallarini bajarishda Braxmagupta(VII asr), musbat va manfiy sonlar ustida kupaytirish va bo'lish amallarini bajarishda Bxaskara kabi matematiklarning xizmatlari katta bo'lgan.

Arablar xukmronlik qilgan mamlakatlarda arab xukmronliginingo'urnatilishi boshda fan taraqqiyotida ancha salbiy ta'sir kursatgan. Keyinchalik u yerlarda savdo sotiq yo'lga qo'yildi, turli xalqlar orasida madaniy alqkalar ma'lum miqdorda rivojlandi. Bu harakatlar uz navbatida SHark mamlakatlarida fanning rivojlanishiga xam yo'l ochib berdi. Sharq mamlakatlari Hindiston va Xitoy bilan savdo-sotiqni yulga quyib, ularning madaniyati, fani, jumladan, matematikaning qulga kiritgan yutuqlari bilan tanishish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ldilar. Bu o'lkalarda katta qurilishlar, suv inshootlari barpo qilish, savdo sotiqni rivojlantirish geografiya, geodeziya, astronomiya, matematika kabi fanlarni rivojlantirishga zarurat tugdirdi. O'rta va Yaqin Sharq mamlakatlaridagi olimlar dastlab yunon (ellinizm davri), Xitoy va Hindiston matematiklarining ishlarini o'rganib, ularni arab tiliga tarjima qilib, ba'zilariga sharxlar yozdilar. Bunga misol Kilib Yevklidning «Boshlangichlar», Ptolomeyning «Almagest», Arximedning «SHar va silindr xdkida», «Aylanano'lchash», «Turtburchak xakida» va boshqa olimlarning bir qancha asarlarini keltirish mumkin. O'rta asrlarda yashab ijod etgan O'rta Osiyolik donishmandlardan Muxdmmad al-Xorazmiy, Abo'l Vafo (16.6.940 y.-998 y.), Ibn al-Xaysam (taxminan 965-1039 yillar), Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Umar Xayyom, Nasriddin Tusiy (18.2.1209 y.—25.6.1274 y.) kabi olimlar matematika va boshka tabiiy fanlarni birmuncha rivojlantirdilar. Muxammad al-Xorazmiy arifmetika, algebra, astronomiya kabi fanlarga doyr asarlar yozib, ularda matematik bilimlarni sistemalashtirdi. Xorazmiy «Al-jabr va alMukobala» asarini ritorik tilda yozib, unda algebraic ifodalar ustida amallar bajarish, birinchi va ikkinchi darajali tenglamalarni yechish kabi materiallarni yoritdi.

Bu kitobdan butun insoniyat kup asrlar davomida matematik bilimlar asoslarini urganib keldi. Optik masalalarni, uchinchi-turtinchi darajali tenglamalarga olib keluvchi geometrik masalalarni yechishda Abu Rayhon Beruniy va Ibn al-Xaysamning xizmatlari katta bo'lgan, Al-Xaysam jismlar xajmini hisoblashda integral tushunchasiga yaqin kelgan.

Trigonometrik funksiyalar qiymatini x, isoblash jadvalini tuzishda Abo'l Vafoning xizmatlari kattadir. U tuzgan jadvalda sinusning qiymatlari juda katta aniqlikda hisoblangan. Nasriddin Tusiy osmoniy jismlarni o'rganish, sferik uchburchaklar va ularning xossalari haqida yetarli darajada aniq ma'lumotga ega bo'lgan. Umar Xayyom algebrani tenglamalar yechish xdkidagi fan deb ta'riflagan. Bu ta'rif utgan asrning oxirlarigacha amalda qullanib kelingan. Keyinchalik algebra fanining keng tarakkiy kilishi natijasida bu ta'rif yetarli bo'lmay koldi, lekin algebra uzining formal amallar haqidagi fan ekanligini saqlab kelmoqda. Umar Xayyom «Mushkulot al-Hisob» asarida musbat butun sondan kvadrat ildiz chiqarishning umumiy koidasini birinchi bo'lib ta'rifladi.

Xayyom Samarkandda yashagan davrida «Algebra» asarini yozib, unda chiziqli, kvadrat va kub tenglamalarni sinflarga ajratib, ularni taeushl kilib, yechish usullarini kursatdi. Umar Xayyom boshchiligida uz zamonasining mashx,ur astronomi va matematiklari Abo'l Abbas Lukoriy, Abdurax,mon Xorazmiy va boshkalar 5 yil qunt bilan birgalikda ishlab, yangi eron quyosh kalendarini (takvimini) tuzdilar. Ular tuzgan kalendarning aniklik darajasi juda katta bo'lib, 450 yilda bor-yugi bir kecha-kunduz (sutka) vaqtiga teng xatolikka yul quyardi. Xayyom (1077) «Uklidus (Yevklid) kitobining qiyin postulatlariga sharxlar» kitobida Yevklidning 5-postulati boshqa gzostulatlarga Karaganda murakkabligini, uni isbotlash uchun juda kup olimlar uringanliklarini ta'kidlaydi. XIX asrning buyuk matematigi N. I. Lobachevskiy goyasining moxiyati xam ana shunday. Xayyom geometriya tuzishda aksiomalar sistemasi tula bo'lishi zarurligini aytgan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Хатамова, З. (2021). Expenditure of income from taxes and levies in the kokand khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *research support center conferences* (No. 18.05).

2. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). SH. VOKHIDOV'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects*, 139-141.
3. Хатамова, З. (2023). Из истории денежной политики в финансовой системе Коканского ханства. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 327–336. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/history-of-uzbekistan/article/view/16511>
4. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). Political-Financial Analysis of the Issues of Science of the Kokand Khanate in the Work of Khudoyorkhonzade “Anjum At-Tavorikh”. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(10), 102-111. Retrieved from <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/463>
5. Burkhonov, I. M. (2020). “ZAKAT” HAS ENSURED FAIRNESS AND BALANCE IN SOCIETY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 201-204.
6. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2020). Negative impact of the tax system on political life-on the example of the history of the Kokand Khanate (1850–1865). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 790-795.
7. Burkhonov, I. (2021, June). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboyev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat. In *Конференции*.
8. Burkhonov, I. (2021). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboyev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1242>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).

9. Бурханов, И. (2023). Научное наследие Шарафиддина Али Язди в интерпретации Асомиддина Оринбоева. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 165–171.
10. BURKHONOV, I. FROM THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF ABURAZZAK SAMARKAND" MATLA'I SA'DAYN AND MAJMA'I BAHRAIN. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 138-144.
11. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). The Importance of Asomiddin Urinboev's Scientific Research in the Study of the History of the Kokan Khanate. *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3, 175-179.
12. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). In the Study of the History of the Kokand Khanate. *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics*, 6, 68-71.
13. Burkhanov , I. . (2022). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV. *International Bo'lletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(10), 63–67.
14. Хатамова, З. (2021, August). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.05).
15. Хатамова, З. Н. Особенности налоговой системы Кокандского ханства / З. Н. Хатамова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 5 (295). — С. 254-256. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/295/66918/>
16. Nazirjonovna, H. Z., & Abdumannobovich, N. M. (2020). Tax system on the territory of kyrgyzstan during the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 209-212.

17. Xatamova, Z. (2020). Expenditure of state funds replenished by taxes in the history of the kokand khanate. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 5(3), 274-277.
18. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ZAKAT IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKANDD KHAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(3), 100-105.
19. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHAN: CUSTOMS TAX AND OTHER COLLECTIONS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(3), 94-99.
20. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). THE ISSUE OF CRAFTSMANSHIP IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *World Bo'lletin of Public Health*, 31, 8-10.
21. Burkhanov I. A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation* (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>
22. Burkhanov I. M. (2024). The Significance of A. Orinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(11), 113-117. <https://doi.org/10.5281/>
23. Burkhanov I. M. (2024). The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14095929>
24. Ilyosxon Muxiddinovich Burxonov Farg'ona, Markaziy Osiyo tibbiyot universiteti (CAMU) o'qituvchisi. (2024). XIV-XV ASR TARIXIGA OID MANBALARNI A.O'RINBOEV TADQIQOTLARIDA AKS ETISHI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14061206>

25. Xatamova Zumradxon Nazirjonovna. (2023). QO‘QON XONLIGI MOLIYAVIY TIZIMIGA ELCHILIK MASALALARINING TA’SIRI: XUDOYORXONZODANING “ANJUM AT-TAVORIX” ASARI ASOSIDA: THE IMPACT OF THE AMBASSADOR’S PROBLEMS ON THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND-KHANATE: ON THE BASIS OF "ANJUM AT-TAVORIH" OF KHUDYAROKHANZODA. *Farg’ona Davlat Universiteti*, 28(5), 12. Retrieved from <https://journal.fdu.uz/index.php/sjfsu/article/view/2192>
26. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). Important Islamic Sources in Studying the Financial System of the Kokan Khan. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(11), 478-481. <https://doi.org/10.5281/>
27. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). The Issue of Financing Material-Architectural Culture in the History of the Kokan Khan. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 4(11), 189–193. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejbsos/article/view/4603>
28. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). An Organic Research of the History of the Turkish Nations: A Social Problem in the Financial System of the Kokand Khanate. *American Journal of Political Science and Leadership Studies*, 1(7), 30–32. Retrieved from <https://semantjournals.org/index.php/AJPSLS/article/view/505>
29. A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation* (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>
30. The Significance of A. Urinboev’s Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. (2024). *Innovative: International*

Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology (2995-486X), 2(11), 26-2 <https://multijournals.org/index.php/innovative/article/view/2633>

